

UK Council for
Graduate Education

UK Research Supervision Survey

2024

In partnership with:

With support from:

Research
England

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UK Council for Graduate Education,
Lichfield Centre, The Friary, Lichfield,
Staffordshire WS13 6QG.

Registered Charity No. 1061495

Email: ukcge@ukcge.ac.uk

Phone: +44 (0)1543 308 602

www.ukcge.ac.uk

X: @ukcge

LinkedIn: ukcge

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Acknowledgements

We gratefully acknowledge all the contributors who helped to produce this report:

From UKCGE:

Dr Owen Gower, Sara Bellan, Dr Annette Rubery.

From the Next Generation Research SuperVision Project (RSVP):

Dr Karen Clegg, Professor Doug Cleaver (particularly for their work on the Conclusions section).

From Shift Insight:

Scott Lampon, Jane Powell, Isadora Rackham, Andy Drzo.

We would also like to acknowledge the support and guidance of key advisers within the Next Generation Research SuperVision Project (RSVP) who helped to shape our research hypotheses, develop the question set in 2024, and encourage doctoral supervisors to respond to the survey:

Dr Alex Pavey at King's College London.

Professor Richard Graham, Rachel Van Krimpen and Dr Connie Wan at the University of Nottingham.

Dr Heather Sears at Coventry University.

Dr Nicola Palmer, Dr Gill Adams, Lucy Clague and Lewis Clark at Sheffield Hallam University.

Dr Tom Jackson and Reena Morar at the University of York.

We also express our thanks to Sheffield Hallam University in particular, who offered its support by approving the research under its research ethics policies and procedures guidelines.

This research was funded by Research England through the Next Generation Research SuperVision Project (RSVP).

This report was designed by Creative Triangle.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13843553

Executive summary

Background and methodology

The UK Council for Graduate Education (UKCGE) serves as the national representative body for postgraduate education and research. In 2021, with support from the Wellcome Trust and UKRI, UKCGE ran the first **UK Research Supervision Survey (UKRSS)**, a UK-wide survey that was open to all those involved in supervising doctoral candidates, providing them with an opportunity to share their experiences.

With funding from Research England, through the **Next Generation Research SuperVision Project (RSVP)**, this survey was repeated in 2024, using an online survey that was live between June 3rd and July 16th 2024 and which obtained 5,174 usable responses. Respondents were involved in the supervision of doctoral candidates in 141 UK institutions.

Supervisors enjoy and value their role

90% of respondents indicated that they enjoyed being a supervisor, consistent with 91% in 2021. In addition, 79% felt that supervision increased the quality of their own research (down from 82% in 2021). There was a small decline in those agreeing that doctoral supervision had become more demanding over the previous five years (65% vs. 68% in 2021).

The primary motivations for supervision were largely centred around supporting candidates in their academic development and career progression. Specifically, 35% of respondents cited the transformation of a candidate into a successful researcher as their main motivation. This was followed by 26% who were driven by the desire to impact candidates' careers, and 25% who found joy in mentorship. These motivations highlight a strong candidate-focused approach. This focus is further reflected in the high percentage of respondents who felt valued by their candidates, with 90% indicating they felt appreciated by them, compared to 92% in 2021.

However, a lower proportion of respondents felt valued by their workplace (56%). As one respondent put it:

"[I need] recognition by the institution. I always [get] recognition by the supervisees."

64% agreed that the reality of supervision matched their expectations. Around a third agreed that supervision made them anxious or that concerns around the role kept them up at night. Further, while 94% of supervisors reported having a good understanding of institutional policies and procedures, and 88% knew how to apply them, the proportion of those who felt supported by their institutions in implementing these practices dropped to 70%.

Perceptions and experiences of candidate diversity

In 2021, 75% of respondents agreed that increasing the diversity of doctoral candidate populations would enhance research culture at their workplace or institution. In 2024, the majority – 68% – still believed that greater diversity would positively impact research culture.

92% of respondents believed they had the interpersonal skills needed to supervise candidates from diverse backgrounds. Meanwhile, 76% felt confident in addressing the mental health and well-being needs of their candidates, and 79% felt confident that they had the intercultural skills necessary for supervising a diverse candidate pool.

Respondents frequently indicated that they were supervising candidates with a prior postgraduate qualification (89%). 40% of the sample were supervising at least one candidate with an undergraduate qualification only.

In terms of candidate characteristics, respondents were most likely to have supervised candidates with English as an additional language (68%) in the previous five years. They reported being least likely to have supervised candidates who had experienced care (5%), perhaps indicating that there are still substantial barriers to doctoral study for this group. 31% had supervised a neurodivergent candidate.

Between 2021 and 2024, there was a decrease in the proportion of respondents who suggested that funding should be targeted to under-represented groups (21% in 2021, decreasing to 16% in 2024).

Workload and capacity continue to be issues

Supervisory workload, identified as a major challenge in our 2021 study, remained significant in 2024, with 29% of respondents citing it as the second most common challenge in supervision. This area was explored in a more granular way this year. The average total number of candidates supervised in total was 5.5, 3.1 of which were in situations where the respondent was a main/primary supervisor.

In line with the results of the 2021 survey, 30% of respondents indicated that their institution had no known policy which limited the number of candidates a supervisor could take on, or that there was a policy that did not specify a limit. Another 34% were unsure whether such a policy existed.

74% of those who reported a policy limiting the number of candidates per supervisor indicated that the policy was monitored, but only 29% indicated that it was *always* adhered to. When time for supervision was part of a workload allocation, supervisors were allocated an average of 42 hours per main/primary supervision candidate. The actual time reported to be spent on this type of supervision was higher than this at 69 hours. In the case of secondary supervision, actual hours spent were 44% higher than the average of those allocated.

While 74% of respondents felt that one to four candidates were optimal, only 20% of policies had a maximum this low. 5% cited a policy maximum of nine or more, a number considered optimal by only 1% of respondents. Supervisors formally supporting three to four candidates were more likely to agree that concerns over their doctoral candidates have kept them awake at night (35%) than those formally supervising one to two (30%).

Trends in supervisory culture: team and rescue supervision

As was the case in 2021, the 2024 responses continued to indicate a rise in team supervision. This year, there has been an increase in the percentage of respondents who suggest they either “frequently” or “always” took part in team supervision over the last five years (71% in 2021, rising to 76% in 2024). 95% said that the supervisory team was comprised of others in their institution, 47% that the team included supervisors from other institutions and 19% that the team would also include supervisors from outside their sector.

70% of respondents working in supervisory teams felt that these teams offered a better experience for doctoral candidates (up from 65% in 2021), with those in teams of over three more likely to agree. 58% indicated that supervisory teams were usually comprised of two people.

Rescue supervision, where a supervisor takes on a candidate previously supervised by someone else, continued to be a trend in the 2024 results: 57% of respondents had taken on a doctoral candidate who had previously worked with a different supervisor, rising to 72% of later-career respondents.

Half of those who had taken on a doctoral candidate from a different supervisor said they received no workplace support when taking on a candidate previously supervised by someone else. 35% reported gaining access to previous reports and documentation and 22% reported being offered transition support.

In both team supervision and rescue supervision, the need for more institutional support was emphasised. When taking over a candidate previously supervised by someone else, 56% of respondents felt that workplace support was only “partially” adequate, with just 36% finding it fully sufficient. Similarly, in team supervision, responses indicated inconsistency in institutional models. 32% of respondents noted that decisions regarding team supervisory roles were made on a case-by-case basis, while another 9% reported these decisions were made informally, and 8% stated they were either poorly defined or not defined at all.

Shifting challenges and the need for institutional support

Challenges faced by research supervisors have changed substantially since 2021 when many were battling issues related to the COVID-19 pandemic. In 2024, the biggest challenge for respondents was fostering a candidate's confidence, focus and engagement, with nearly two-thirds of respondents reporting this (59%).

We also saw an increase in the proportion citing candidates' mental health or personal issues as a challenge (20% in 2024 compared with 15% in 2021) and candidate issues with funding / financial issues (17% in 2024 compared with 10% in 2021). Supporting candidates with mental health issues was also one of the areas in which supervisors had the least confidence; 25% did not see this as part of their role at all.

Similar to the results in 2021, the most common suggestion for enhancing the supervisor experience in 2024 was the need for more dedicated time to focus on their candidates and research, with 42% of respondents emphasising this as a key area for improvement, up from 40% in 2021. Consistent with the 2021 survey, in 2024 42% felt that the introduction of doctoral training partnerships or centres has improved the doctoral candidate experience.

At the end of the survey, respondents were asked for their suggestions for improving research supervision. A number of themes emerged, including respondents wanting more time (or an improved distribution or balance of available time) to spend on supervision, better recognition or support of their supervisory practice from institutions, increased funding opportunities, and improved pastoral and financial support networks for candidates.

Recognition of supervision time and its value by institutions

Recognition of both the time invested in supervision and the value of supervisory practice was a recurring theme in the 2024 responses. While 74% of respondents noted that their workplace or institution formally acknowledged supervisory responsibilities in workload allocation to some degree, many expressed a desire for a more concrete acknowledgement of the time dedicated to supervision.

"[I need] Better recognition of the time it takes to perform this role. Academia is vastly under-estimating the time and effort each of our academic tasks is requiring."

There was a slight increase in the perceived value of supervision, with 56% of respondents in 2024 believing that their workplace or institution values research supervision, up from 52% in 2021. 24% of respondents said their workplace did not offer awards for excellent supervision, nor did it consider supervision in promotion criteria. 63% of respondents who said supervision was assessed within promotions criteria indicated that this was assessed via the number of successful candidates.

Continuing professional development for supervisors

75% of respondents reported that continuing professional development (CPD) was available at their institution, a figure that remains relatively stable compared to 2021, when 73% reported the availability of CPD. There has been a slight increase in the proportion of respondents who indicate that this training is both mandatory and occurs regularly, rising from 25% in 2021 to 29% in 2024.

79% were satisfied with their ability to be an effective supervisor (compared to 75% in 2021) and respondents were largely confident of their abilities in a range of areas of supervision. This confidence increased substantially when their institution offered regular mandatory research supervisor CPD.

90%

of respondents enjoy being a supervisor

79%

say supervision increases the quality of their own research

Respondents' understanding of their institution's policies and procedures surrounding supervisory practice have remained consistent since 2021. Those who were aware of or had engaged with UKCGE's **Good Supervisory Practice Framework** had greater awareness of these policies and procedures (88%) than those who were unaware of it (68%).

- While 83% felt confident in advising and signposting further support for careers, 34% did not see providing advice on non-academic careers as part of their role and 45% were not regularly doing this.
- While 92% indicated confidence in their interpersonal skills in supervising doctoral candidates from diverse backgrounds, 79% agreed that they had the required intercultural skills.
- Supervisors were least likely to agree that they were confident in responding to mental health and well-being needs of their candidates (76%).
- 69% of respondents agreed that their role in doctoral recruitment is clear, but 50% agreed that they were clear about how to access doctoral funding.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and research objectives

Established in 1994, the UK Council for Graduate Education (UKCGE) is the national representative body for postgraduate education and research. In 2021, with support from the Wellcome Trust and UKRI, UKCGE ran the first **UK Research Supervision Survey (UKRSS)**, a UK-wide survey offering those involved in doctoral supervision an opportunity to share their experiences. In 2021, the UKRSS received 3,435 responses. In 2024, the survey was revised and repeated, receiving 5,174 usable responses.

The aim of the 2021 UKRSS was to help UKCGE and the broader postgraduate community gain a deeper understanding of the complexities of modern research supervision, including how it is acknowledged and rewarded. The aims of the UKRSS in 2024 are to further develop our understanding of the nature of research supervision, as well as to delve into how supervisory practices and cultures have changed since 2021. The **Next Generation Research SuperVision Project (RSVP)** – who funded the 2024 research – will use its findings to identify opportunities for enhancing the support available to doctoral supervisors and to provide insights into the changing culture of research supervision.

We are grateful to all those who participated in the 2024 survey, as well as to those who contributed to our research questions and to the survey script. Our research questions in the 2024 UKRSS explored the following questions:

1. How has the supervisory landscape changed since the 2021 UKRSS report?
2. How do supervisors perceive and approach their responsibilities – including to their doctoral candidates, their fellow supervisors, their institutions, and the academic community at large?
3. What forms of training, support, reward, recognition, and promotion exist within institutions for supervisory practice?
4. What motivates supervisors to provide thoughtful and effective supervision? What has changed in their perception of thoughtful supervision since 2021 and what are the perceived barriers to effective supervision?
5. How have supervisors handled the doctoral landscape surrounding diversity, equity, and inclusion, and mental health and well-being?
6. What is the role of doctoral supervision in building a positive and inclusive research culture and community? How can institutions better support their research culture?

1.2 Methodology

The survey

The 2021 online survey was developed by Shift Learning (part of **Shift Insight**) in collaboration with the staff and trustees of UKCGE, as well as representatives of the Wellcome Trust and UKRI, alongside several other expert advisors. This year, the survey was developed further through collaboration between Shift Learning and UKCGE, informed by an evaluation of the 2021 survey data, alongside input from the **Next Generation Research SuperVision Project (RSVP)**.

The survey consisted of 48 questions in total, covering the following broad themes:

- The characteristics of those who are supervising.
- How candidates are recruited and selected.
- Supervision workload, recognition and reward.
- Support given to research supervisors.
- Team supervision situations.
- How supervisors perceive and approach their responsibilities.
- Motivations for becoming involved in research supervision.

In 2021, the survey report included findings from additional focus groups but in 2024, we did not run additional focus groups to supplement the survey results. The research was cleared by the research ethics process at Sheffield Hallam University, under the authority of Professor Doug Cleaver (Chair, UKCGE).

Survey dissemination

The survey went live on June 3rd 2024 and was kept open until July 16th 2024. An invitation and live survey link were emailed to 6,252 potential respondents by UKCGE, while Shift Learning sent the same details to its panel of 1,446 UK researchers. Potential respondents were incentivised with a £250 prize draw. Doctoral candidates were omitted from the survey at an early point. Respondents did not have to be currently supervising to complete the survey, provided they had had recent experience of doctoral supervision.

Overall sample size and reliability

We received a total of 5,174 usable responses, a substantial increase on the 3,435 received in 2021.

While there was an increase in survey responses, it remains difficult to estimate the overall sample size of active research supervisors in the UK, and, therefore, to give an accurate indication of the sample size against the total population. Our survey found that an average of 3.1 doctoral candidates are formally assigned to each research supervisor as their primary/principal supervisor. Given that there are approximately 116,000 doctoral candidates enrolled in the UK¹, this suggests a total of approximately 37,400 primary supervisors; we surmise that this survey collected the views of around 11% of supervisors in the UK, who reported that they were currently primary or principal supervisors (n = 4,187).

¹ HESA data for 2022/23, released in August 2024.

As noted in the project limitations section of this report, respondents were self-selecting. It is feasible that this may have led, for example, to a greater response from those with a larger number of candidates, for whom the study might have seemed more important. If this were the case, the actual number of research supervisors would be somewhat higher.

Data cleaning and analysis

Prior to data analysis, poor quality and highly partial responses were removed. New derived variables were created, e.g. ranges of numerical questions, means, modes and medians. A random sample of 1,000 responses from each open question was selected to be analysed using closed codes devised by Shift Learning and agreed with UKCGE.

Data from 2021 was imported into the 2024 data set for detailed comparison wherever possible. Comparisons between the different years' surveys were collected in a tracking grid. Changes to questions and answer options are noted within the report.

Q Research software was used for data analysis. By default, Q conducts various tests of statistical significance on tables, such as independent t-tests and Chi-square tests, where applicable. Multiple-comparisons correction has been applied where appropriate.

Questions were analysed with particular attention to:

- Individual characteristics, e.g. role, career stage, subject, gender identity, ethnicity, age, region and sexual orientation.
- Institutional characteristics, e.g. institution type.
- Supervision characteristics, e.g. supervision workload, engagement with the UKCGE framework.
- Survey wave (2021 vs. 2024).

Relationships between other relevant questions in the survey were also explored.

Only differences indicated to be statistically significant are reported here. A p-value of 0.05 is used for significance testing. We checked the data size of each significant result to ensure that we felt confident in reporting on it – for example, that there is a sufficient n size of a given cell (e.g. >10).

1.3 Project limitations

Participation in the research was voluntary, so the sample of supervisors here is self-selecting, itself a potential biasing factor. In addition, while the sample is large, it was obtained via UKCGE and Shift Learning channels. There may be supervisors, particularly in non-higher education sectors, who were not known to us, and were not consulted as a result.

While we sought to keep questions static to make comparisons between our 2021 and 2024 data, in some cases changes were made to questions or answer options to provide greater data accuracy or to improve the user experience. Where questions are not entirely comparable, we have noted this within the report.

As some of these changed questions were used to make up the profile of respondents, weighting the sample accurately to match the 2021 survey was not possible. However, review of the profile of respondents suggests that the sample broadly matches the 2021 survey, as discussed in the next section of this report.

2. Profile of respondents

2.1 Job role and specialism

In line with 2021, the 2024 survey found that 92% of participants held academic positions. However, there was a slight increase in the number of respondents working as research staff, teaching staff and postdoctoral researchers. Additionally, a new category for healthcare professionals was introduced in 2024. Please refer to the [appendices](#) to see job role by career stage.

The proportion of participants specialising in Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences (AHSS) in the 2024 survey increased by 1% to 41%, with Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) making up 59%. As was the case in 2021, Biological Sciences held the largest representation of survey respondents (12%). This was followed by Engineering (8%), Business and Management Studies (6%), Education (6%), Computer Science and Informatics (5%), and Public Health, Health Services and Primary Care (5%). A detailed breakdown of subjects by category can be found in the [appendices](#).

Job role

Figure 1. Which of the following best describe(s) your role? Base n = 5,174.

Career stage

Figure 2. How would you describe your current career stage? Base n = 5,174.

2.2 Workplace and institution

Respondents were involved in supervising doctoral candidates in 141 institutions. The top ten institutions by number of respondents are indicated below.

Top 10 Institutions		
Institution	%	No. of responses
King's College London	4%	212
University of Manchester	4%	204
University of Glasgow	4%	184
University of Sheffield	4%	174
University of Cambridge	3%	161
University of Southampton	3%	161
University of Edinburgh	3%	147
University College London	3%	143
University of Leeds	3%	124
Durham University	3%	124

Table 1. At which UK institution(s) do you currently supervise doctoral candidates? Base n = 4,828.

Please refer to the [appendix](#) for a comprehensive list of all universities mentioned.

Mission Group

Provider type

Figure 3. Coded and grouped from Q: At which institution(s) do you currently supervise doctoral candidates? Base n (2024) = 4,720. Base n (2021) = 3,253.

2.3 Institutional representation

Of the 141 institutions mentioned, 71% of respondents in the 2024 survey were employed at pre-1992 institutions, while 27% were at post-1992 institutions. In 2021, 68% of participants were based at pre-1992 institutions. In both the 2021 and 2024 surveys, 52% of respondents worked at Russell Group institutions. However, in 2021, the second most represented mission group after the Russell Group (excluding Unaligned) was MillionPlus at 4%. By 2024, the University Alliance had become the second most represented group, with 7% of respondents, up from 3% in 2021.

74% of respondents had previously worked with a different employer within the same sector, while 34% had experience in a different sector (e.g. transitioning between industry and academia). Respondents from post-1992 institutions were more likely to have worked in a different sector (42%), with this being especially common among those in Business and Management (51%) and Education (49%).

2.4 Respondent demographics

48% of respondents identified as male and 46% identified as female. The remainder of respondents were made up of those who identify as non-binary or gender non-conforming (1%) or those who preferred not to say (5%).

Most respondents identified as being of white ethnic backgrounds (88% of those based in the UK and 62% of those based internationally). Among respondents based outside the UK, just over a quarter considered themselves to belong to an ethnic minority in their country of residence.

Ethnicity (UK)

- Non-white ethnic minority
- White
- I'd prefer not to say

Figure 4. Please choose the option that best describes your ethnic group or background. Base n (2024) = 3,057. Base n (2021) = 3,435;

Part of an ethnic minority (International)

- Yes
- No
- I'd prefer not to say

Figure 5. (Only shown to those outside the UK) Do you consider yourself part of an ethnic minority in your country of residence/workplace/institution? Base n = 1,766

Respondents were represented from across the UK, with the largest proportions residing in London (12%) and Yorkshire and the Humber (12%), followed by the South East (11%). Northern Ireland had the fewest respondents in 2024 (3%), though its share increased from 2% in 2021. Wales, the West Midlands, and the North East each accounted for 5% of the responses.

For additional details on respondent demographics, please refer to the [appendices](#).

3. Background of current doctoral candidates

3.1 Academic background of candidates

Academic background of doctoral candidates

Figure 6. Please indicate the academic background of the doctoral candidates you are currently supervising, either formally or informally. Multiple choice question. Base n = 4,177. Question not comparable to 2021 results due to change in question structure. Unsure not shown in chart = 1%.

Respondents most frequently indicated that they were supervising candidates with a prior postgraduate qualification (89%). 40% of the sample were supervising at least one candidate with an undergraduate qualification only. Supervisors at Russell Group institutions were slightly more likely to be supervising candidates with only an undergraduate qualification (45%) than supervisors at other institutional mission groups.

Although no further comparisons can be made between 2021 and 2024, it is worth noting that in 2021, 2% of respondents reported supervising candidates without any prior higher education qualifications. By 2024, this figure had decreased to 1%.

3.2 Journeys into doctorates

89% of respondents were supervising at least one candidate who had come directly from a previous higher education qualification, and 23% were supervising only these candidates.

Half of respondents were supervising at least one UKRI-funded candidate and 39% were supervising at least one candidate sponsored by their employer to undertake a doctorate.

Background of doctoral candidates

Figure 7. Please indicate the background of the doctoral candidates you are currently supervising who are... Derived variable created by combining 'Some (1%-24%)' with 'Many (25%-49%)' and 'Majority (50%-74%)' with 'Vast majority (75%-99%)'. Base n = 4,173-4,174.

Respondents were significantly more likely to be only supervising candidates coming directly from a previous higher education qualification if they were affiliated with mathematical sciences (59%), physics (49%) and chemistry (41%).

Although a direct comparison is not possible due to slight differences in the phrasing of the questions between 2021 and 2024, the primary disciplines reporting that their candidates were coming directly from previous higher education qualifications were Biological Sciences (97%), Physical Sciences (96%), and Language and Literature (92%) in 2021.

3.3 Type of doctoral programmes followed

Supervisors had most frequently supervised candidates enrolled for a single subject Doctoral programme. This has dropped from 71% in 2021 to 66% in 2024. In 2021, the majority of respondents had the most experience with supervising on single-subject PhDs. This was consistent across demographics, with the exception of those at non-academic institutions, which were most likely to supervise on Collaborative Doctorates than other institution types.

In 2021, 69% of respondents indicated that they had never supervised a candidate in a collaborative doctoral programme. By 2024, this percentage rose to 73%.

All other figures are largely consistent with 2021.

3. Background of current doctoral candidates

Doctoral programmes of candidates

Figure 8. How frequently have you supervised candidates enrolled for the following doctoral programmes in the last five years? Base n = 5,139-5,141.

3.4 Characteristics of doctoral candidates

Respondents were most likely to have supervised candidates with English as an additional language (68%) and least likely to have supervised those who had experienced care (5%), perhaps indicating that there are still substantial barriers to doctoral study for this group.

Characteristics of doctoral candidates

Figure 9. Have you supervised doctoral candidates with the following characteristics in the last five years? Base n = 5,157.

Where answer options remained the same since 2021, figures have remained consistent. Supervisors at post-1992 institutions were significantly more likely than their counterparts at pre-1992 institutions to have supervised mature candidates (39% vs. 21%). They were also more likely to have supervised candidates with caring responsibilities (52% vs. 42%).

4. Recruitment and selection of doctoral candidates

4.1 Views on the recruitment process

In the 2024 survey, two additional agreement statements were included in a set of questions related to the clarity of doctoral funding and roles. This change aimed to gain a deeper understanding of respondents' views on the doctoral recruitment process, following the 2021 findings that highlighted supervisors' dissatisfaction with it.

The remaining statements remained consistent with those in the 2021 survey, allowing for direct comparison; most of these statements did not show statistically significant changes over time.

My role in doctoral recruitment is clear

Figure 10. To what extent do you agree with the following statements? Derived variable created by merging 'Strongly disagree' with 'Disagree' and 'Strongly agree' with 'Agree'. Base n (2024) = 5,097-5,105.

In one of the new statements this year, 71% of respondents agreed that their role in doctoral recruitment is clear, while equal parts (14%) disagreed or neither agreed nor disagreed. Respondents from Russell Group institutions were more likely than average to agree that their role in doctoral recruitment is clear (74% compared with 71% overall).

For example: 40% agreed that the recruitment and selection process was a "good predictor of whether the candidate will become an independent researcher" in 2024 (an identical proportion agreed in 2021). 67% agreed that their priorities in selecting a doctoral candidate aligned with that of their institution (again an identical proportion agreed in 2021).

The notable exception was a decline in the percentage of respondents who believed that increasing the diversity of doctoral candidate populations would enhance the research culture at their workplace or institution. This view decreased from 75% in 2021 to 68% in 2024.

4.2 Access to doctoral funding

In a new question for 2024, 50% of respondents agreed that they were clear on how to gain funding for doctoral candidates, while 28% disagreed. Those who had engaged with the UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework were more likely to agree with most statements regarding the recruitment and selection of doctoral candidates. For example, 59% of those who had engaged were clear on how to gain funding for doctoral candidates, compared with 50% overall.

I am clear on how to get funding

Figure 11. To what extent do you agree with the following statements? Full statement: "I am clear on how to get funding for doctoral candidates." Derived variables created by combining 'strongly' and 'somewhat' options. Base n (2024) = 5,097-5,105.

4. Recruitment and selection of doctoral candidates

Respondents from Russell Group institutions were more likely to agree with the statement than average (55% compared with 50% overall).

In 2021, 48% of respondents agreed that access to doctoral funding was allocated based on a candidate's research potential, increasing to 53% in 2024.

However, much as in 2021, respondents continued to report issues related to recruitment in their survey responses. A recurring theme was the desire among supervisors for more equitable recruitment practices, particularly concerning funding:

“The funding process could be improved so that we have more suitable candidates. The doctoral training centre approach is too dominant in the allocation of PhD places; it should be used for a small number of PhDs in targeted areas, perhaps 5% of total PhDs, and a more predictable DTP allocation based on previous research excellence for the majority of PhD places.”

“One thing that would significantly enhance my role as a research supervisor is improved access to resources and funding. By having improved access to resources and funding, the quality and impact of research conducted under my supervision would significantly increase, benefiting both the students and the broader academic community.”

“[An improvement would be] having better funded students, the current PhD salary is too low and that creates problems with recruitment and with the quality of current PhD students' work.”

Several respondents specifically emphasised that funding challenges disproportionately affect under-represented communities, creating barriers to accessing doctoral studies:

“[I need] the university to strongly support and prioritise funding for under-represented candidates from minoritised backgrounds in our field, which is extremely strongly homogenous and poor in representation.”

“[I would like] an increase in funding for candidates from under-represented and disadvantaged backgrounds, both to support taking up doctoral studies and to support activities alongside study.”

90%

of respondents indicated that they enjoyed being a supervisor

4.3 Recruitment of more funded candidates

76% of respondents agreed that there should be more opportunities to recruit funded doctoral candidates in their specialisms. This was in comparison to 71% in 2021.

This year, there was a decrease in the proportion of respondents who suggested that funding should be targeted to under-represented groups (21% in 2021 vs. 16% in 2024).

Research staff and professional services staff were more likely to suggest that funding should be targeted (21% and 36%, respectively, vs. 16% overall). Those working in Education and Sociology were also significantly more likely to agree that funding should be targeted (26% and 31%, respectively, vs. 16% overall).

The percentage of respondents who suggested the higher education sector, or their specialism, is recruiting too many candidates remained low, at 7%, the same as in 2021. Respondents from an Arts, Humanities or Social Sciences discipline were slightly more likely than average to say there should not be more opportunities to recruit funded doctoral candidates (9% compared with 7% overall).

5. Supervisory workloads

5.1 Number of candidates

A key aim of this year's survey was to collect more granular data around supervisory workloads. Respondents were asked to indicate the number of candidates that they supervised on both a formal and informal basis.

The average number of candidates supervised in total was 5.52, 3.1 of which were in situations where the respondent was a main/primary supervisor. This was similar across all institution types.

How many doctoral candidates are you currently supervising?				
	Average	Mode	Median	Base n
As a main/primary supervisor	3.1	1	2	1,314
As a secondary supervisor	2.5	1	2	1,299
Informally	2.2	1	1	489

Table 2. Question was asked in 2021, but small wording changes to options and with ranges given, rather than as a numeric question. Averages include only those undertaking this form of supervision.

The number of candidates for which respondents were the main supervisor varied by career stage – those in their early career were most likely to be supervising one or two candidates (81% vs. 52% overall), while those in late career were more likely to be supervising five to ten candidates (24% vs. 17% overall).

5.2 Policies around the number of candidates to be supervised

In line with the results of the 2021 survey, 30% of respondents indicated that their institution had no known policy which limited the number of candidates a supervisor could take on, or that there was a policy, but they thought it did not specify a limit. Another 34% were unsure whether such a policy existed, including 31% of those with main supervisory responsibilities.

² Comparative data is not available for 2021 due to changes in the way this question was asked.

Interestingly, supervisors at post-1992 institutions were more likely to report that their institution had a known policy limiting the number of supervisees (44%). Similarly, 44% of respondents from University Alliance institutions reported having such a policy, compared to 34% of those from Russell Group institutions. This difference was particularly marked for those in STEM specialisms.

Nearly three-quarters (74%) of respondents who reported an institutional policy on the number of supervisees indicated that their institution monitored compliance with this policy. However, only 29% said the policy was always followed. Only 8% reported that no known monitoring was in place, but another 18% stated they were unsure.

Number of candidates per supervisor: official policy vs what is considered optimal by supervisors

Figure 12. What is the maximum number of candidates a supervisor can supervise at any one time at your workplace? Base n = 1,742, only those stating a limit shown. In your view, what is the optimal number of candidates per supervisor? Base n = 4,857.

5.3 Formal recognition of time spent

74% of respondents indicated that their workplace/institution formally recognised supervisory responsibilities in their workload allocation to some extent. Of these respondents, 40% indicated that they did not know the number of hours allocated per doctoral candidate. Lack of workload recognition was more likely for those describing themselves as “postdoc” (47%), “healthcare professional” (27%) or “research staff” (22%) than it was for those describing themselves as “academics” (15%). It was also more likely to be the case for those in STEM subjects (21% vs. 11% of those in AHSS).

However, it is important to note that responses frequently highlighted concerns about the quality, level, or accuracy of recognition. Some respondents expressed frustration that the acknowledgement of their workload, time commitments, and the value of their supervision in promoting research culture was notably insufficient:

“[I need] great recognition and [acknowledgement] of the work I put into the role e.g. promotion recognition and better time allocation for supervision, including time allocation for personal development / further training to be an even better supervisor.”

“[I need] proper recognition of the amount of time it takes to do the role well (we don’t even have a workload model in our department, let alone one that includes PhD student supervision).”

“[I would like to have] more time to undertake ad hoc supervisory or pastoral meetings with my student. Having more time to work on publications with my student. Feeling like the department leadership team valued research at all – I don’t feel valued by the department for any of my contributions to research. It would be nice to have some recognition in terms of either time or funding to attend retreats for writing or conferences with my student.”

“I wish I had received more recognition for the 33 PhD students that got their PhD under my supervision. A bonus would have been nice, a simple word of thanks from the Dean or VC also.”

“[I need] greater recognition of the complexity of the role. Realistic recognition in work loading, currently the hours given are a disgrace and reflect lack of value in the role.”

There was no observed relationship between the likelihood supervision was recognised in workloads and the number of candidates for which respondents were the main supervisor, suggesting perhaps that decisions are taken on an institutional rather than an individual basis.

Does your workplace/institution formally recognise your supervision of these candidates in your workload allocation?

Figure 13. Base n (2024) = 5,088, answer options changed from 2021. Analysis includes only those undertaking some form of supervision currently.

5. Supervisory workloads

5.4 Allowance per candidate

Unsurprisingly, respondents were allocated most time to candidates when they were their main supervisor (an average of 42 hours per year for each candidate). Allocations where a respondent was a secondary supervisor were approximately half this.

84% of those supervising informally reported no hours allocated per candidate.

Please specify how many hours are allocated per year per candidate for ...?				
	Average	Mode	Median	Base n
Candidates where you are the main/primary supervisor	42	50	40	1,314
Candidates where you are the secondary supervisor	20	10	20	1,229
Candidates you are supporting informally	0.6	0	0	489

Table 3. Question asked in 2021, but small wording changes to options and with ranges given, rather than as a numeric question. Averages include only those undertaking this form of supervision and where an allocation of hours was in place.

5.4 Time spent per year on supervision

While supervisors were allocated an average of 42 hours per main/primary supervision candidate, the time reported to be spent on supervision was higher than this, at 69 hours per year. In the case of secondary supervision, actual hours spent were double those allocated, with respondents reporting spending 40 hours per year on supervision compared to the allocated 20.

Average hours supporting individual doctoral candidates per year

Figure 14. On average, how many hours over the course of a year would you estimate you spend supporting each individual doctoral candidate you support? Base n = 1,314 (main), 1,229 (secondary), 489 (informal). Only those who were involved in these supervision types. Please specify how many hours are allocated per year per candidate ... Base n = 1,314 (main), 1,254 (secondary), 497 (informal).

When multiplied by the number of candidates they were supervising, the average gap between institutionally allocated time and time spent each year is apparent.

- Main/primary supervision – 72 hours per year.
- Secondary supervision – 44 hours per year.
- Informal supervision – 50 hours per year.

6. Supervisory culture

6.1 Changes to doctoral study

In 2021, 20% of respondents agreed that entrants' preparedness for doctoral study had improved over the past five years, while 34% disagreed. By 2024, agreement had decreased to 17%, and disagreement had risen to 40%, suggesting a growing perception that entrants are less prepared for doctoral study.

Conversely, a majority of respondents continued to view the complexity of doctoral study had increased. In 2024, 51% of respondents felt that complexity had increased, compared to 54% in 2021. 21% of respondents in 2024 believed that the complexity had not increased over the past five years.

Entrants' preparedness for doctoral study has improved within the past 5 years

The complexity of doctoral study has increased over the past 5 years

Figure 15. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about doctorate entrants? "In my personal experience of supervising candidates..." Derived variable created by merging 'Strongly disagree' with 'Disagree' and 'Strongly agree' with 'Agree'. Base n (2024) = 4,888-4,927. Base n (2021) = 2,793-2,806.

6.2 The impact of doctoral training centres

This year, 42% of respondents agreed that the introduction of doctoral training partnerships or centres has improved the doctoral candidate experience, staying largely consistent with 2021 findings.

Figure 16. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements: "The introduction of doctoral training partnerships or centres has improved the doctoral candidate experience." Derived variable created by merging 'Strongly disagree' with 'Disagree' and 'Strongly agree' with 'Agree'. Base n = 5,097-5,105. n = 0-3,435.

6.3 Motivations

When asked in an open question what motivates them to be an effective supervisor, the top three motivations for supervising students were primarily student-focused, suggesting that supervisors were largely driven by the goal of helping students to succeed rather than by their own research, professional or personal interests. These motivations included a focus on student development (35%), the impact on candidates' careers (26%) and a commitment to students (16%). Additionally, supporting future academics (15%) and mentorship (25%) were key factors.

Following these student-centred motivations, reasons related to professional and personal satisfaction came next, including personal and professional commitment (24%) and personal satisfaction (20%). Thematic interests in research, such as research interest (25%), love of knowledge and learning (17%) and interest in the subject matter (14%) were secondary to these primary motivations.

6. Supervisory culture

Motivations to be an effective supervisor

Figure 17. What motivates you to be an effective research supervisor? Open question, coded. Not directly comparable to 2021 results due to change in code frame. Base n = 966.

“Seeing the growth and development of the trainees and interacting with them once they have graduated. This is incredibly rewarding, and one of the best parts of being an academic.”

“It’s one of the best parts of the job: talking to someone smart about their ideas and helping them to realise a piece of coursework (dissertation/thesis) that gets them a qualification. Ideally, it’s also about training a future colleague, though postdoc funding tends to be dire. Plus, it’s nice to have a change from teaching first-year undergraduates, as an intellectual gear-change, so it’s motivating to be an effective research supervisor to get the most out of the time with the PGRs.”

“Training the next generation of scientists is the most important and rewarding part of the academic job. It is such a unique dynamic with a huge impact on a candidate’s degree, welfare, and career that it is essential to continually evaluate effective approaches as a supervisor.”

While 11% of respondents cited past experiences as their motivation, those who did highlighted it as a significant driving factor:

“I had a terrible supervisor, and the relationship ultimately broke down after the (horrendous) viva. Having persevered through this, I am very motivated to provide effective supervision and a good viva experience.”

“I had a really bad supervision experience when I was doing my PhD. My relationship with my supervisor had broken down and she didn’t attend my viva or congratulate me. I want to ensure the students I work with don’t experience that and feel supported.”

“I did not have a great experience as a student but had a great post doc mentor and so I want to be able to provide candidates with a supportive and challenging environment as part of their PhD training.”

6. Supervisory culture

There were no statistically significant differences between how supervisors responded to this question when looking at institution type or mission group, subject specialism, career stage or personal characteristics. This suggests that supervisory motivations are uniform across UK institutions.

6.4 Attitudes to supervision

Supervisors' agreement with broad attitudinal statements about supervision remained largely consistent with 2021. The vast majority enjoy being a supervisor (90%), most are satisfied with their ability to be an effective supervisor and feel that supervision has a positive impact on the quality of their own research work.

“Research supervision is one of the best features of working in a research-active HEI. Helping to direct the growth and development of talented, intelligent and motivated individuals to achieve their potential is an enormous privilege.”

Late-career academic

Their enjoyment and valuation of supervision was consistent throughout responses:

“I enjoy working with research students – both the creation of new knowledge and supporting their journey through the doctorate and into meaningful careers. It is the best part of my role as an academic.”

“It’s definitely one of the best parts of the job! You’re at the cutting-edge of research, learning along with the candidates while helping them discover their identity as researchers and develop their skills.”

“It is my favourite part of the job seeing my team grow and become independent researchers. I love my group and its diversity. I love the long-term impact of the training, both personal and professional development, that I can have.”

I enjoy being a supervisor

I am satisfied with my ability to be an effective supervisor

Being a supervisor increases the quality of my own research

However, agreement around supervisor anxiety has also remained consistent with 2021 results. Supervisors were again more likely to agree that concerns over their doctoral candidates have kept them awake at night if they were formally supervising three to four candidates (35%) than those formally supervising one to two (30%).

6. Supervisory culture

Over the last 12 months, concerns over supervision of doctoral candidates have kept me awake at night

Supervising doctoral candidates makes me feel anxious

Doctoral supervision has become more demanding over the past 5 years

The reality of being a supervisor has matched my expectations

Figure 18. To what extent do you agree with the following statements? Derived variable created by merging 'Strongly disagree' with 'Disagree' and 'Strongly agree' with 'Agree'. Base n (2024) = 4,849-4,907. Base n (2021) = 2,802-3,435.

As in 2021, STEM supervisors were more likely than AHSS supervisors to agree that concerns over their candidates have kept them awake at night (32% vs. 26%) but were also more likely to agree that being a supervisor increases the quality of their own research (82% vs. 75%).

6.5 Research culture and supervision

83% of respondents agreed that their institution lived up to the provided definition of a positive research culture: one which is “supportive, open, diverse, inclusive, collaborative, and creative”.

Those supervising at Russell Group institutions were more likely to agree with this statement (86%) than their counterparts supervising at other mission group institutions, such as University Alliance (79%) and GuildHE (77%). Those supervising at post-1992 institutions were most likely to disagree with the statement (12%).

Institutional positive research culture

Figure 19. To what extent do you agree that doctoral supervision in your institution lives up to the following definition: A positive research culture is supportive, open, diverse, inclusive, collaborative, and creative. Derived variable created by merging ‘Strongly disagree’ with ‘Disagree’ and ‘Strongly agree’ with ‘Agree’. Base n = 5,095.

6. Supervisory culture

Increasing the diversity of doctoral candidate populations would improve the research culture at my workplace/institution

Figure 20. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? Derived variable created by merging 'Strongly disagree' with 'Disagree' and 'Strongly agree' with 'Agree'. Base n (2024) = 4,849-4,907. Base n (2021) = 2,802-3,435.

As in 2021, female supervisors were significantly more likely to agree with this statement (74%) than their male counterparts (66%).

6.6 Supervisors' confidence

Over three-quarters of supervisors felt confident in their supervisory skills and abilities. Supervisors were least likely to agree that they had the confidence to respond to the mental health and well-being needs of their candidates (76%), or the intercultural skills to supervise candidates from diverse backgrounds (79%).

3/4

Over three-quarters of supervisors felt confident in their supervisory skills and abilities

Confidence in supervisory skills and knowledge

Figure 21. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements relating to your skills and knowledge as a doctoral supervisor? Derived variable created by merging 'Strongly disagree' with 'Disagree' and 'Strongly agree' with 'Agree'. Base n = 4,910-5,108.

6. Supervisory culture

Those supervising at post-1992 institutions were slightly more confident than their counterparts supervising at pre-1992 institutions about responding to candidate's mental health and well-being needs (80% vs. 75%). Female supervisors were also more confident than their male counterparts in this area (82% vs. 73%).

There were slight differences in supervisor confidence in their interpersonal and intercultural skills depending on whether they had engaged with the UKCGE's Good Supervisory Practice Framework. 96% of supervisors who had engaged with the framework were confident in their interpersonal skills, compared to 92% who had not.

This difference was smaller when looking at intercultural skills, with 81% of those who had engaged with the framework feeling confident here, compared to 79% of those who had not.

Significant differences between those who had and had not engaged with the framework in relation to other skills explored in this question have been outlined in the chart below:

Confidence in supervisory skills and knowledge

Figure 22: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements relating to your skills and knowledge as a doctoral supervisor? Derived variable created by merging 'Strongly disagree' with 'Disagree' and 'Strongly agree' with 'Agree'. Cross analysed with "Have you engaged with the UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework?" Derived variable created by merging "No, but I am aware of it" with "No and I am not aware of it". Base n = 4,834 – 4,886.

Supervisors who had engaged with the **Good Supervisory Practice Framework** were also slightly more likely to feel confident supporting candidates to publish in their field (97% vs. 95%) and feel confident in advising candidates about and signposting career support (84% vs. 83%), but these differences were not statistically significant.

6. Supervisory culture

6.7 Supervisors' understanding

Since 2021, respondents' understanding of their institutional policies and procedures related to supervisory practice has remained relatively stable, with 94% indicating that they are aware of the policies and procedures for monitoring candidate progress.

The largest difference is around awareness of policies and procedures in the event of a breakdown in the supervisory relationship, which has dropped by 10% from 85% in 2021 to 75% in 2024. Respondents' awareness in this area was higher if they were formally supervising three to four candidates (81%) or five to ten (80%) than their counterparts formally supervising one to two (75%).

I am aware of my institution's policies and procedures in the event of breakdown in the supervisory relationship

I understand my institution's policies and procedures for monitoring candidate progress

I know how to enact my institution's procedures surrounding supervision of candidates

Figure 23. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements relating to your skills and knowledge as a doctoral supervisor? Derived variable created by merging 'Strongly disagree' with 'Disagree' and 'Strongly agree' with 'Agree'. Base n (2024) = 4973-5015. Base n (2021) = 3,372-3,426.

Respondents who knew about or had engaged with UKCGE's Good Supervisory Practice Framework had greater awareness of these policies and procedures (88%) than those who had not encountered the Framework (68%).

Despite generally high levels of understanding and awareness of policies and procedures, respondents were less likely to feel supported in enacting effective supervision practices, a trend consistent with 2021.

While 94% of supervisors reported having a good understanding of institutional policies and procedures, and 88% knew how to apply them, only 70% felt supported by their institutions in implementing these practices and addressing related issues.

6. Supervisory culture

I feel supported to enact good supervision and address issues in practice

Figure 23 (continued).

While we did not ask anything else directly on this issue, a few responses to the survey's final open questions – asking which single thing could be done to best improve respondents' experience of research supervision – shed light on this. Respondents mentioned experiencing a lack of support when things went wrong in their supervisory relationships, and the absence of an effective university-wide support system for students, which creates a burden on supervisors.

6.8 The role of the doctoral supervisor

Respondents' perceptions of which tasks fall within a supervisor's remit have remained largely consistent since 2021 – the highest proportion agreed that supervisors should highlight training, professional development, and public engagement opportunities (93%), and the fewest agreed they should provide advice on non-academic careers (66%).

Agreement that tasks fall within remit of supervisor role

Figure 24. (2024) "I consider it my role as a doctoral supervisor to ..." Multiple choice. (2021) "To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements relating to your role as a doctoral supervisor?" Chart shows agreement with corresponding statements. Derived variable created by merging 'Strongly agree' with 'Agree'. Base n (2024) = 5,023. Base n (2021) = 3,435.

6. Supervisory culture

In the open responses, some queried expectations around supervisors having such a broad and varied role in relation to those they supervised:

"I feel there is also a problem of expectations. I do not think it is my role as a supervisor to end up being the psychologist of the students that have poor mental health. However, I do it because I care and because that increases the chances of a successful PhD. However, it should not be an expectation from the supervisor, otherwise we are researchers, supervisors, tutors, psychologists, friends, supporters, etc., of the PhD candidates. This ends up blurring the roles, which ends in problems."

Mid-career academic.

Those supervising at Russell Group institutions were significantly more likely to agree with each of these statements than their counterparts supervising at unaligned or other mission group institutions. Similarly, those supervising STEM subjects were also significantly more likely to agree than those supervising AHSS subjects. The only exception here was in providing pastoral support, which was selected by 78% of respondents in Russell Group universities, compared with 82% of those at University Alliance and unaligned institutions, and 80% of those at MillionPlus institutions.

Male supervisors were significantly more likely than female supervisors to consider their role to include ensuring their candidates publish in their field (82% vs. 77%) and providing advice on pursuing both academic careers (92% vs. 88%) and non-academic careers (70% vs. 62%). Female supervisors were more likely than male supervisors to include being a role model in terms of work/life balance for their candidates (74% vs. 67%).

"Having a consistent and supportive research environment is the single thing that could be done to improve research supervision. I think we need a 'village' to enable doctoral and scholarship success. One or two individual supervisors cannot do it all."

Mid-career academic

In my supervisory work, I regularly...

Figure 25. "In my supervisory work, I regularly ..." Multiple choice question. Base n = 5,023.

The relationships present in the results of the role perception question are also present here – Russell Group and STEM supervisors were more likely to carry out each of these tasks (apart from providing pastoral care), male supervisors were more likely to ensure that candidates publish in their field and provide advice on both academic and non-academic careers, and female supervisors were more likely to be a role model in terms of work/life balance.

6. Supervisory culture

6.9 Post-completion support

In the 2024 surveys responses, respondents reported having carried out post-completion support for their candidates largely in alignment with 2021. 66% of respondents reported frequently writing references for further employment, compared to 77% in 2021.

52% of respondents stated that they frequently had collaborated or co-authored on publications post-completion in 2024, compared to 56% in 2021. Although other activities were less common, it was rare for supervisors to never engage in post-completion activities. This suggests that many supervisors continue to offer support to their supervisees in some capacity even after their formal supervisory relationship has ended.

Frequency of post-completion support activities

Figure 26. How frequently have the following occurred in the last five years? Base n = 4,962-4,963.

6.10 The impact of being a doctoral examiner

63% of respondents agreed that their role as a doctoral examiner had a positive impact on the quality of their supervision. 17% of respondents stated that their role as an examiner had no impact on their supervisory practice.

Impact of being a doctoral examiner duties on supervision

Figure 27. To what extent does any work you are committed to as a doctoral examiner impact the quality of your supervision of your own candidates? Derived variable created by merging 'Weak negative impact' with 'Strong negative impact' and 'Weak positive impact'. Base n = 4,857.

Respondents were more likely to indicate that doctoral examination had a positive impact on their own supervision if they were male (67%) or self-described as late career (71%). This positive impact also increased with the number of candidates a respondent was formally supervising.

“Current students appear to face increasing mental health challenges, more frequently present with learning profiles/as neurodivergent; many appear to have lowered ambition, poor focus, less motivation and passion; lack confidence and enquiry skills. Work ethic has also changed and students appear to expect a more structured and partly taught experience.”

Mid-career academic

6. Supervisory culture

6.11 Challenges

Challenges faced by research supervisors have changed substantially since 2021, when many were battling issues related to the COVID-19 pandemic. In 2024, the biggest challenge for respondents was fostering a candidate's confidence, focus and engagement, reported by nearly two-thirds of respondents (59%). This is a notable increase from 2021, where only 14% mentioned this as a challenge.

Top 5 challenges from 2024 and 2021

2024	2021
<p>34% Supervisor's lack of time and high workload</p>	
<p>15% Mental health / personal issues (candidate)</p>	
<p>14% Difficulties due to COVID-19 / remote supervision</p>	
<p>14% Fostering candidate's confidence / focus</p>	
<p>10% Candidate issues with funding</p>	

Table 4. "What are your biggest challenges in supporting and motivating candidates to progress and thrive?" Open question, coded. Only top five responses shown. *due to employment or other commitments. Base n (2021) = 1,405, Base n (2024) = 989.

Issues around fostering confidence, focus and engagement related to several factors:

- Dealing with candidates whose confidence, motivation and resilience were seen to have declined post-pandemic, and which were harder to address in an increasingly remote setting with less face-to-face contact.
- Working with candidates who had other commitments, for example those who were continuing full or part-time work or had caring responsibilities.
- Managing candidates who had additional support requirements due to personal characteristics such as neurodivergence, health or mental health conditions or because they were educated in systems outside the UK.

Candidate's mental health and personal issues have become an even greater challenge, cited by 15% in 2021, increasing to 20% in 2024.

Supervisors' lack of time and high workload continued to be an issue in 2024, with 29% reporting this challenge – though this was mentioned less than in 2021 (34%).

More respondents reported funding and financial issues for candidates in 2024 (17%) compared to 2021 (10%). This may reflect broader sector challenges around funding and the cost-of-living crisis. Funding and financial issues may also link to candidates' lack of time due to employment and other commitments, which increased from 4% in 2021 to 17% in 2024 – potentially indicating that more candidates have additional jobs to support themselves.

There were few differences in the challenges faced by research supervisors with different characteristics in 2024, suggesting that challenges are broadly universal. However, one notable difference in 2024 is that respondents from post-1992 universities were more likely to report candidates' lack of time was a challenge (25%) than those in other institution types, particularly pre-1992 (12%). Respondents in Russell Group universities were less likely to cite this as a challenge (11%).

7. Supervisory practice

7.1 The nature of team supervision

This year, there has been an increase in the percentage of respondents who suggest they either “frequently” or “always” took part in team supervision over the last five years. In 2021, 93% of respondents had taken part in team supervision, with 71% suggesting they do this “always” or “frequently”, and 65% agreed that “team supervision offers a better experience for the doctoral candidate”. In 2024, 76% of respondents indicated that they “always” or “frequently” took part in team supervision, and 70% of respondents working in supervisory teams felt that these teams offered a better experience for doctoral candidates.

The size of the supervisory team most frequently comprised two people (58%), consistent with 2021. However, at Russell Group institutions, supervisory teams were more likely to consist of two people, with 62% of respondents indicating this as the typical team size.

This year, we also asked respondents who work within a supervisory team who else was part of the supervisory teams they had experienced. 95% said that supervisory teams involved other supervisors in their institution, 47% said that teams included supervisors from other institutions, and 19% suggested that it would also include supervisors from outside their sector. Smaller

supervisory teams are more likely to be working with others in their own institution, whereas those in teams of four or more are more likely to be working with supervisors from other institutions and other sectors (6% compared with an average of 4%).

7.2 Definition of roles in team supervision

This year, respondents were asked a new open question about how roles were defined in team supervision. Respondents interpreted the question in different ways, and answers were often assigned to multiple elements in our code frame, which were not mutually exclusive. This partly reflected the wide range of models of team supervision. 32% of respondents indicated that decisions around roles were made on a case-by-case basis. Another 9% reported that these decisions were made informally and another 8% that they were either ill-defined or not defined at all.

While some stated that decisions around responsibilities were clearly defined at the point of an offer to a student for study, others described the situation as “fluid” or “difficult to define”.

Although in 12% of cases respondents described situations of co-supervision, with two or more supervisors with equal levels of responsibility and time allowance, this was not true in most cases. Teams generally had a defined primary supervisor role, although the tasks undertaken by this lead supervisor varied. In many, though not all cases, this lead supervisor would set the “academic direction” and take responsibility for the bulk of administrative tasks associated with a candidate, such as ensuring compliance with university regulations or visa requirements. In some cases, these administrative tasks were distributed across a team or delegated by the most senior supervisor to more junior team members.

Teams generally followed one of the below models:

- Structured by subject expertise, particularly for interdisciplinary PhDs.
- Structured by methodological expertise, in some cases led by a supervisor with subject expertise and supported by methodological experts specific to the research.
- Structured by location, with external supervisors, either in other academic institutions or industry generally having fewer administrative responsibilities.

In most cases, meetings appeared to be attended by all supervisors, though in some cases, where there were more than two supervisors, the third (or those beyond) might be required only to attend meetings and not provide written feedback, or to provide less granular feedback.

Responsibility for pastoral care varied hugely – this was sometimes seen as the responsibility of the primary supervisor, but in other cases delegated to others.

There were no notable differences by individual or institutional characteristics.

Most of my candidates are part-time students with no PhD funding so balancing study with work is always a challenge.
Late-career academic

7.3 Marginality and supervisory practice

In the 2021 report, some respondents noted that gender-based power dynamics were prevalent in supervisory practices, affecting interactions with other supervisors, institutions, and occasionally candidates. The 2024 survey found that issues related to gender and race remain significant themes, particularly in relation to colleagues and supervisory teams.

In open-text responses, respondents often took the opportunity to state that their experiences of gender or race had an impact on their supervisory practice. Occasionally, their experiences of marginality were then motivators for respondents' supervisory practice:

"I learn so much from the PhD candidates that this motivates me to find ways to effectively shape their research and writing for successful outcomes. In cases where I have worked with female candidates from the Arab world, I am also motivated by trying to provide them with the best opportunities to develop and then contribute back to their home countries."

"I want my students to succeed and achieve the best outcome from their abilities. As a woman of minority, I have faced many challenges during my PhD, including being dismissed, bullied (by male professors and research staff), discriminated against compared to male colleagues, or not getting all the support I could have. It has only made me want to make it easier and more "pastoral", to use your words, for the PhD students I supervise. True, as a woman, I had to work ten times harder (and sometimes more) than my male colleagues to prove my worth. For the students (women and other minorities) I've supervised, I just want them not to have to work harder than their colleagues. Furthermore, to progress, research needs diversity. So, by encouraging minorities, I contribute my humble share to increase the diversity of perspectives and fresh ideas."

Respondents also reported that their supervision experiences often involve power dynamics, where supervisors must invest more time and effort, even though the first supervisor or a male counterpart may receive more of the credit for the work:

“Informal supervision is never recognised. As a Black woman from a working-class background, many postgrad students approach me for support and advice, especially when they are struggling. The support I give is not necessarily visible, so is not valued in any way. I find that the proposals that come to me via my university department I turn down because they are not in my field of expertise. Often these are from overseas students.”

“[I need] more time and support. I am a second supervisor but often act as an informal first supervisor as I read all work and provide detailed feedback. Not the case with first supervisor I work alongside with (we share two students). First supervisor gets all the credit when student successfully completes. Also like to point out gender differences – female students feel closer to me and we (female supervisors) are often overlooked in terms of our workload and support when supervising. There needs to be a sector model of PhD supervision. At the moment, lots of differences in terms of support.”

76%

There has been an increase in the percentage of respondents who suggest they either ‘frequently’ or ‘always’ took part in team supervision over the last 5 years (71% in 2021, compared to 76% in 2024).

7.4 The success of team supervision

70% of respondents working in supervisory teams felt that they offered a better experience for doctoral candidates than single supervisors, compared to 65% in 2021.

Team supervision offers a better experience for the doctoral candidate.

Figure 28. To what extent do you agree with the following statement? “Team supervision offers a better experience for the doctoral candidate”. Derived variables created by combining ‘Strongly’ and ‘Somewhat’ for both agree and disagree. Unsure not included. Base n (2024) = 4,979.

Those in supervisory teams of three people were more likely than average to agree that the experience was better for doctoral candidates (78% compared with 70% overall).

However, respondents working in STEM fields were notably less likely to agree that team supervision provides a better experience for doctoral candidates, with 67% in agreement compared to the overall average of 70%. In contrast, those in the AHSS fields were more likely to view team supervision favourably, with 75% agreeing that it enhances the doctoral candidate experience.

7.5 The extent of rescue supervision

In the 2024 results, there has been a slight decrease in the percentage of respondents who suggested they had taken on a doctoral candidate who had previously worked with a different supervisor (59% in 2021 compared with 57% in 2024).

However, this increased to 72% when looking only at later-career respondents. Those working in Business and Management Studies (75%), Education (79%) and English (75%) were all more likely to have done so than average (57%).

Respondents from Russell Group institutions were less likely than average to suggest they had ever taken on a doctoral candidate who was previously working with another supervisor (55% compared to 57% overall).

59% of those who had taken on a candidate previously supervised by someone else said this was due to the previous supervisor moving institutions (58% in 2021) while 36% said this was due to a complaint or problem with a previous supervisor (37% in 2021). 10% suggested that there was a bullying or harassment complaint against the previous supervisor, a slight increase from 2021 data (8% in 2021).

7.6 Support when taking on a previously supervised candidate

Half of respondents said they received no workplace support when taking on a candidate previously supervised by someone else.

Support offered when taking on a candidate previously supervised by someone else

Figure 29. “Have you had any of the following workplace support when you have taken on a candidate previously supervised by someone else?” Base n (2024) = 2,896.

Early-career respondents were significantly more likely to say they had received additional mentoring and advice from senior colleagues (22% compared with 8% overall). 38% of those working in Mathematical Sciences who had taken on a doctoral candidate previously supervised by someone else said they had received transition support, such as meeting with the previous supervisor – significantly higher than the overall average of 22%. There were no other significant differences by subject affiliation.

56% of respondents felt the access to workplace support was “partially” adequate, while only 36% suggested this was completely adequate. 18% of those who received “other” workplace support said it was not at all adequate, significantly higher than the 5% average.

49% of respondents who received additional mentoring or guidance from senior colleagues said that their support offered was completely adequate, with 49% also saying this was only partially adequate.

8. Recognition and valuing supervision

8.1 The value of supervision

There was a slight increase in the proportion of respondents who believe research supervision is valued by their workplace/institution (52% to 56%). This also represents a small increase in the average, 3.1 to 3.2, between 2021 and 2024.

Figure 30. "In your view, how much is research supervision valued by your workplace/institution?" Derived variables created by combining 'extremely and 'somewhat' options. Base n (2021) = 3,380-3,395. Base n (2024) = 4,774-4,808.

91% of respondents this year felt research supervision was valued by doctoral candidates, consistent with 2021. 92% said they valued it themselves, compared to 93% in 2021.

Overall, 56% of supervisors reported that they felt valued by their institution. 36% of respondents reported feeling undervalued by their institution. Respondents from Russell Group institutions were more likely than average to suggest that their institution valued research supervision (59% compared with 56% overall).

Recognition of the value of supervision was highlighted by respondents as a need from institutions:

"[I need] clearer recognition of the importance of supervision in the purpose of the University, to include generous time allocation and explicit distinction from one's own research goals, where those goals also need more generous time and space."

“[I need] better recognition for the importance of the doctoral supervisor role by my University, particularly in relation to supervising professional doctorate students who are often overlooked and/or treated differently to PhD students by the University.”

63% of respondents who said supervision was assessed within promotions criteria indicated that this was assessed via the number of successful candidates.

Respondents from pre-92 institutions were more likely to indicate that supervisions were evaluated in promotions criteria based on the number of current candidates they supervised, with 43% affirming this, compared to 41% overall.

8.2 Reward systems

24% of respondents said their workplace/institution does not offer awards for excellent supervision, nor does it consider supervision in promotions criteria.

Among respondents who felt that supervision was valued at their workplace or institution, only 15% reported that their institution did not provide any rewards for it. In contrast, 36% of those who felt their institution undervalued supervision said their workplace did not offer rewards or consider supervision in promotion criteria, compared to 24% overall. This suggests a link between the availability of rewards or consideration of supervision in promotions criteria and respondents' feelings of being valued by their workplace or institution.

63%

of respondents who said supervision was assessed within promotions criteria indicated that this was assessed via the number of successful candidates.

9. Continuing Professional Development (CPD)

9.1 Provision of continuing professional development

While the proportion of respondents indicating that research supervisor CPD was available in their institution has not significantly increased since our last survey (73% in 2021 and 75% in 2024), there has been an increase in the proportion who say that this CPD is mandatory and takes place on a regular basis, rising from 25% in 2021 to 29% in 2024.

Those supervising candidates at specialist and GuildHE institutions were more likely to report regular mandatory CPD was provided (44% and 48%, respectively)

The provision of mandatory regular research supervision CPD strongly related to how supported supervisors felt by their institution across many areas, as shown in [Figure 31](#).

There was also a large difference between the feelings of institutional support experienced by those receiving mandatory regular CPD compared to those receiving one-off, non-mandatory CPD.

For example, while 91% of those receiving regular mandatory CPD felt supported by their institution in understanding their policies and procedures for monitoring candidate progress, only 72% of those receiving one-off non-mandatory CPD felt supported in this area.

We saw similar differences in how confident supervisors felt across the range of skills related to their role. For example, while 81% of those receiving regular mandatory CPD agreed that “I feel confident to respond to mental health and well-being needs, signposting candidates to further support where appropriate”, this figure fell to 71% for those not receiving research supervisor CPD. Similarly, 96% of those receiving regular mandatory CPD agreed that they “Understand my institution’s policies and procedures for monitoring candidate progress”, compared to 85% of those whose institution did not provide CPD.

42% of those who had engaged with the UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework supervised in institutions with mandatory research supervisor CPD, compared to 24% of those who were not aware of the framework.

Many respondents took the opportunity to explain that more opportunities to undertake continuing professional development would be helpful:

“[I need] more dedicated time for CPD related to supervisory practice e.g. time for training courses or to keep up to date with pedagogical literature related to supervision.”

“One thing that would make my role as a research supervisor better is having access to additional resources for professional development and training in mentorship techniques. This could include workshops, seminars, and access to a network of experienced supervisors to share best practices. Enhanced training would enable me to better support my students, address their diverse needs more effectively, and stay updated on the latest developments in research supervision. This, in turn, would improve the overall research experience for my students and contribute to their success.”

Some took the opportunity to say that the mandatory CPD they have experienced is often not satisfactory or timely for enhancing supervisory practice:

“As an early career researcher, despite the mandatory training on offer at my university, it felt very general, and I am not particularly clear on ‘how’ to supervise. My own experience as a PhD supervisee was poor, so I have some awareness of how ‘not’ to do it! But the finer details of what to do, when, how etc. is not made clear. I appreciate there isn’t an explicit format for this, but greater opportunities for mentoring/shadowing to learn from other, more established/experienced supervisors could be beneficial. I speak with colleagues to learn from them, but I’m frequently told ‘You know what you’re doing – just be confident in yourself’ – but this isn’t a lack of confidence – I don’t know what I don’t know, and this makes me anxious.”

9. Continuing Professional Development

“[I need] more training and support for supervisors to aid [their] supervision CPD – we have nothing except supervisor refresher training with very basic topics covered. I had a difficult student to supervise and there was no support within the university for me or the other supervisor to help us navigate through the situation.”

Furthermore, some respondents explained that the mandatory CPD provided by their institutions did not touch on ‘soft skills’ of supervision or more specific guidance on relationship maintenance:

“[I need] more useful training instead of just covering the regulations and procedures. For example, some training in mentorship and other soft skills around supervision.”

“[I would have liked] training before becoming a supervisor. We have mandatory training, but this has occurred in the summer, when this time last year, I did not have my job and was not a supervisor. More regular training from universities would be good, e.g. throughout the year, not just before the September intake (which is not when ALL students arrive, just the majority of them).”

“[I would like] better training and support around neurodiversity and specific learning conditions.”

“I would like to see better training being offered by my university – a wider range of training, not just in methods but in other areas such as ethics, social theory, epistemology, etc.”

My workplace/institution adequately supports me with...

Figure 31. “To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the support available to you from your workplace/institution?” “My workplace/institution adequately supports me with ...” and “Does your workplace/institution provide or support research supervisors with continuing professional development (CPD)?” Base n = 4,866-4,875. Figures show agreement, derived variable created by merging ‘Strongly agree’ with ‘Agree’.

9. Continuing Professional Development

9.2 New supervisor CPD

The proportion of supervisors who indicated that 'new supervisor' induction CPD is available at their institution has increased since 2021, from 66% to 70%.

Provision of new supervisor CPD

Figure 32: Is 'new supervisor' induction training available at your workplace/institution?
Base n (2024) = 4,957. Base n (2021) = 3,435.

Respondents working at an institution where new supervisor CPD was mandatory were more likely to agree with each of the statements around confidence in their skills and understanding explored earlier in this report. The areas in which this gap was widest are shown below:

Agreement with supervisor skills and understanding

Figure 33. “To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements relating to your skills and knowledge as a doctoral supervisor?” % agree filtered by respondents at institutions with mandatory new supervisor training and respondents at institutions with no new supervisor training. Derived variable created by merging ‘Strongly disagree’ with ‘Disagree’ and ‘Strongly agree’ with ‘Agree’. Base n (mandatory training) = 3,384-2,465. Base n (no new supervisor training) = 121-124.

9.3 Supervision enhancement activities

The levels at which supervisors have been taking part in supervision enhancement activities have stayed largely consistent since 2021; the largest difference between the results is participation in mandatory updating sessions, which has increased from 30% in 2021 to 38% in 2024.

Supervisors in 2024 were more likely to have carried out each supervisory practice if they had engaged with the UKCGE's Good Supervisory Practice Framework. The largest differences here were participating in events such as supervisor forums (carried out by 59% of those who had engaged with the framework compared to 33% of those who had not) and reading the scholarly literature surrounding supervisory practice (carried out by 52% of those who had engaged with the framework, compared to 21% of those who had not).

How supervisors enhance their practice

Figure 34. “Which of the following do you do to enhance your supervisory practice?” Base n (2024) = 4,939. Base n (2021) = 3,435. Cross analysed with “Have you engaged with the UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework?” Derived variable created by merging ‘No, but I am aware of it’ with ‘No and I am not aware of it’. Base n = 4,939.

9. Continuing Professional Development

Those supervising AHSS subjects were significantly more likely than their STEM counterparts to take part in several supervision enhancement activities. The largest differences were consulting their institution's handbook or code of practice (63% vs. 51%) and participating in supervisor forums (43% vs. 32%).

Awareness of and engagement with UKCGE's Good Supervisory Practice Framework has increased slightly since 2021. The proportion of supervisors who have used it has increased from 12% to 15%.

Engagement with and awareness of UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework

Figure 35. "Have you engaged with the UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework?"
Base n (2024) = 4,939. Base n (2021) = 3,435.

Female supervisors were also significantly more likely to take part in several activities than male supervisors, including consulting their institution's handbook or code of practice (63% vs. 50%), reading scholarly literature surrounding supervisory practice (27% vs. 23%), and participating in both mandatory and voluntary updating sessions (42% vs. 34%, and 34% vs. 27%, respectively).

Respondents at post-1992 institutions were more likely than their counterparts at other institution types to have engaged with the framework (20%). The same is true of supervisors at GuildHE (31%) and MillionPlus (29%) institutions, compared to their counterparts at University Alliance (17%) and Russell Group (12%) institutions. Those supervising in AHSS subjects were more likely to have engaged (17%) or be aware (25%) of the framework than STEM supervisors (13% and 20%, respectively).

9.4 Opportunities for development

Supervisors indicated that development opportunities listed in **Figure 36** were provided by their workplace at similar levels to 2021. 63% of respondents reported they were either 'always' or 'frequently' provided with opportunities to be part of a wider supervisory team as a less-experienced supervisor, up from 60% in 2021.

In 2021, 27% indicated that their institution "always" or "frequently" provided opportunities to learn from more experienced supervisors through role modelling or shared practice. This rose to 56%, including respondents who have such opportunities "occasionally", with 13% saying they never have such opportunities. In 2024, 20% stated that they were "frequently" provided with opportunities to learn from more experienced supervisors through role modelling or shared practice.

Similarly, in 2021, 29% of respondents indicated that their institutions "always" or "frequently" provided opportunities for the mentoring of supervisors, rising to 55% including the respondents who said this happened occasionally. In 2024, 26% of respondents reported that their institutions "always" or "frequently" provided opportunities for mentoring supervisors.

Interestingly, 27% of respondents said they rarely have informal types of support such as time or space for groups within departments or institutions, with 22% reporting they "never" had such opportunities in 2024. In 2021, 47% of respondents said they were "rarely" or "never" provided with the time or space to create informal support groups (compared to 49% in 2024).

9. Continuing Professional Development

Frequency of development opportunities

Figure 36. "How often does your workplace/institution provide the following?" Base n = 4,923-4,927.

9.5 Workplace support

Respondents were asked to what extent they agreed that their workplace offered adequate support across a variety of areas. While high proportions of respondents continued to report they were adequately supported in understanding policies and procedures for monitoring candidate progress (79%) and in the event of a breakdown in supervisory relationship (58%) and how they enact these procedures (72%), the proportions were notably lower than in 2021 (82%, 63% and 75%, respectively).

Agreement with adequate support in the workplace

Figure 37. “To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the support available to you from your workplace/institution?” Only responses with notable differences between years shown. Base n (2021) = 3,435. Base n (2024) = 4,866-4,870.

9. Continuing Professional Development

In 2024, this change may have been driven by early-career respondents who were notably less likely to agree with these statements. There was also a decline in support for highlighting training, professional development and public engagement opportunities – falling from 69% in 2021 to 65% in 2024.

However, while there may be a decline in support around procedures, respondents in 2024 were more likely to agree that there was adequate support in ensuring their doctoral candidates published within their field (33% in 2024 vs. 29% in 2021). This was particularly the case for STEM respondents (68%) and respondents who identified as male (54%). Another notable increase from 2021 was around being a work/life balance role model for candidates – 23% of respondents in 2024 agreed compared to 20% in 2021.

The proportion of respondents agreeing there is adequate support for addressing mental health and well-being queries has remained the same (53% in both years of the survey).

Additionally, despite a drive to increase diversity across the sector, only 31% of respondents agreed they had adequate support in acquiring interpersonal skills and just 27% agreed they had support in acquiring intercultural skills to supervise candidates from diverse backgrounds.

These proportions are lower than the overall proportion agreeing with a combined statement in 2021 (33%). In 2024, those in STEM were more likely than those in AHSS to agree they had support in acquiring these skills (34% and 29% vs. 28% and 25%, respectively).

Agreement with adequate support in the workplace

Figure 38. “To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the support available to you from your workplace/institution?” Base n (2021) = 0-3,435. Base n (2024) = 4,866-4,875.

Research culture played a part – those who disagreed with or were neutral regarding the statement that their institutions have a positive research culture were also more likely to disagree that they received adequate support at their workplace in all areas.

Overall, in 2024, those who were not aware of the UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework and had not engaged with it were more likely to report that they disagreed there was adequate support at their workplace in all areas – suggesting that continued promotion of the Framework is necessary.

10. Improving research supervision

As in 2021, the most popular suggestion for improving the supervisor experience was to allow more time for supervisors to focus on their candidates and research, with 40% of respondents expressing this need. By 2024, this desire remained strong, with 42% of respondents highlighting the need for more dedicated time as a key area for improvement.

The most significant proportional change in suggestions between 2021 and 2024 was the increase in respondents asking for better support or recognition from their institution, which rose from 12% to 25%. In 2024, the desire for more support or recognition became the second most frequently cited improvement, overtaking the call for a reduced or more balanced workload, which held the second spot in 2021. Following this, respondents also expressed a strong desire for improvements to funding structures or increased funding.

42%

wanted more time for supervision

1/3

agreed that supervision made them anxious

20%

found dealing with student mental health a challenge

Main suggestion for improvement to supervisor experience

Figure 39. “What one thing would make your role as a research supervisor better?” Open question, coded. Base n (2024) = 1,000. Base n (2021) = 1,399.

10. Improving research supervision

Below is a sample of the kinds of recommendations offered by respondents to the survey.

Area	Participant recommendations
More time for students and research	<i>PhD timelines should be more guided by individual research, rather than pretending all PhDs are the same and forcing all candidates to conform to exactly the same timeline.</i> Mid-career academic
Better recognition or support from institution	I wish I had more support from the university on supervision. There are some vague workshops on 'leadership' or 'line management' but they really are too nebulous to offer any real advice or solutions. Early-career academic
Changes to funding structure or increased funding	More funding! Doctoral schools are great from a student perspective but have not compensated for the elimination of direct studentships, which means that many students are not able to pursue the research they are passionate about and there are too few coming through the system to fill the postdoctoral positions that are focused on research areas outside the remit of doctoral schools. Late-career academic
Personal or financial support for students	Better wider support structures for students so that supervisors aren't expected to know everything about everything. For example, I shouldn't have to help a student with housing issues – the university should step up and provide that support, but in reality, their support isn't tailored for international students or those with caring responsibilities. Mid-career academic
Reduced or more balanced workload	More workload hours that adequately reflect the amount of time required to do a good job, so that I can manage my work/life balance as I often have to read and feed back on their work on evenings and weekends. Mid-career academic
Less admin and bureaucracy	Clear and effective administration. There are plenty of administrators, it is the circuitous bureaucracy, inflexibility, offloading administration onto supervisors and students, and blame when a date is missed or a form filled out incorrectly. All of this is time consuming and frustrating. Mid-career academic

Area	Participant recommendations
Greater training, CPD or mentorship opportunities	<p>More training and support for supervisors to aid their supervision. CPD – we have nothing except supervisor refresher training with very basic topics covered. I had a difficult student to supervise and there was no support within the university for me or the other supervisor to help us navigate through the situation.</p> <p>Anonymous</p>
Better quality of candidates	<p>Being able to get rid of PhD students who are clearly not good enough, but that is not allowed so we have to waste a huge amount of time and resources on these students over many years, just so they can scrape a PhD without providing us with publishable data.</p> <p>Mid-career academic and research staff</p>
A support group, network or special interest group	<p>A community of practice for supervisors to share experiences close to my own Department/School, because my own learned experiences from one or two students is insufficient to fully develop.</p> <p>Mid-career academic</p>

Table 5. Participant recommendations.

11. Conclusions

11.1 Introduction

The 2024 UK Research Supervision Survey provides a rich, empirical dataset full of insights into the research supervisory experience. This largest ever sampling of UK supervisors is also supplemented by direct statements from those working in this relatively little-explored aspect of Higher Education (HE). Taken together, these perspectives expose strengths and weaknesses in the ways research supervision is designed, managed, recognised and rewarded.

Like its predecessor in 2021, this survey was motivated by the UKCGE's aim to "champion and enhance postgraduate education and research". Further, it aligns with the goal of the Research England-funded Next Generation Research SuperVision Project (RSVP) to "transform the culture and practice of research supervision". As such, the survey represents a clear evidence base on supervision for the many stakeholders in doctoral education, particularly those seeking to bring positive change to the sector. These include policymakers, funders, leaders and change agents in HEIs, supervisors within and outside of HE and, of course, doctoral researchers.

In addition to new data, this report has been calibrated against intelligence from policy documents, pedagogy and ongoing work on supervisory practice that is currently being conducted within RSVP. In this conclusion, therefore, we pull out key points raised by the survey data and reflect on what they imply about the role of supervision within a positive research culture. In the spirit of enabling culture change, we also provide considerations for change agents at differing levels of granularity: Funders; Research Organisations; Doctoral/Graduate Schools; and Supervisors themselves.

11.2 Observations on the data

Supervisor satisfaction

Despite the significant pressures currently being experienced across the UK's HE sector, the survey paints a very positive picture of the research supervisory community. Overwhelmingly, **supervision is considered valuable, rewarding and enjoyable by those who undertake it, often benefiting them in ways that feed into their own research.** Additionally, supervisors gain motivation from the satisfaction of supporting their candidates' development, and by how appreciated they are by those candidates. As in 2021, however, supervisors' views on how valued they are by their institutions (56%) is significantly lower than their perceptions of being valued by their candidates (91%).

Challenges

The biggest challenges reported in the survey pertain to the **support of individual candidates**. A significant 59% of respondents highlighted issues with fostering candidates' confidence, focus and engagement – this is a very concerning figure. **Challenges specifically related to candidate mental health were raised by 20% of participants in 2024, a clear rise from the 15% who flagged this in 2021.**

This is an area where supervisors, unsurprisingly, report relatively low levels of confidence, with 25% indicating that they do not consider it part of their role.

17% of supervisors reported challenges related to **funding and financial issues**. This is a 70% increase on the 10% of participants who raised this in 2021. It is not possible to drill down into the survey data to determine how these financial issues relate to different categories of candidate (i.e. those receiving bursaries, on postgraduate loans, other self-funding routes). However, it is relevant to note that the UKRI PhD stipend level has fallen steadily in real terms since 2004 when, following the recommendations of the Roberts review, they were set just below the tax-free equivalent of average graduate starting salaries. The consequence of 20 years of sub-inflation increments is that the UKRI stipend level (which is also adhered to by the majority of UK HEIs) is now approximately the same as the net National Living Wage.

In 2024, the National Living Wage increased by 9.8%, whereas the UKRI stipend uplift was 3.3%. This may be a specific economic barrier to those who simply cannot commit to years on what amounts to the minimum wage, given their family or broader status.

Continuing Professional Development (CPD) for supervisors

UKRI's New Deal for Postgraduate Research states:

“Good supervision is fundamental to getting good outcomes for the PGR student, research team, Research Organisations, funder and future employer’ and that ‘All PGR students should have access to high quality supervision.... Research Organisations should ensure that everyone in the supervisory team is well supported, including through induction for new supervisors and Continuous Professional Development (CPD)”

This was further emphasised in the revised **UKRI Statement of Expectations on Doctoral Training** (January 2024) which requires research organisations to “invest in their continuous professional development as a supervisor, including building awareness of mental health, well-being, bullying and harassment, and equality, diversity and inclusion issues”.

In this policy context, it is reassuring to note that the reported provision of professional developmental support for supervisors has increased over the last three years. 75% of respondents reported that CPD is available at their institution. Just under a third (29%) said that this was mandatory. Additionally, 70% of respondents said that induction for those *new to supervision* was made available (up from 66% in 2021).

Importantly for culture change, 91% of respondents who had experienced *mandatory induction* felt able to enact their institutions' procedures around supervision compared to 66% of those for whom it was not mandatory. In addition, **those reporting engagement with regular, ongoing CPD consistently felt more confident in their ability to be effective supervisors, to be responsive to their candidates' mental health needs and to have the required understanding of policies and procedures.**

Overall, supervisors who engage in regular, mandatory CPD reported higher levels of confidence in all areas of supervisory practice. Whilst this provides an argument for increase in mandatory supervisor CPD we invite some caution and consideration of the nature and format this might take. For example, to gain confidence in the ability to support individual difference and diversity (where confidence is low – see [Figure 39](#)) requires a particular kind of CPD.

In UKRSS 2021, the “valued by institutions” measure was shown to be improved by the availability of opportunities for mentoring, reflection and engagement in support groups [Ch4, Clegg, Houston and Gower (2024)]. Despite this, in the current survey **just 20% cited opportunities to learn from more experienced colleagues, 21% reported taking part in mentoring, and just 13% had opportunities to reflect on their supervisory practice.** However, the opportunity for role modelling and sharing of practice has doubled (56% in 2024 up from 27% in 2021) indicating that there is a growing awareness of the value in peer learning from peers. Focus groups conducted as part of the RSVP (2024) suggest that these types of peer-to-peer activities appeal strongly to more experienced supervisors, perhaps because they provide opportunities to consider supervision within the broader context of academic practice.

Rather than jump to the obvious conclusion that supervisors need 'training', what the data suggests is the need for a nuanced approach to CPD. This may require a shift in thinking and expectations and an exploration of how to support and learn from experienced supervisors at different career stages. Pragmatically it may also mean looking at the physical and virtual space (and time) for peer discussion, sharing of practice and opportunities to learn from each other, in addition to providing opportunities to demonstrate understanding of policies, principles, procedures to serve consistency and quality assurance.

Team supervision

76% of respondents said they “frequently” or “always” took part in team supervision over the last five years. Typically, this was two people, a main or principal supervisor and a second supervisor. It was common for both supervisors to be present at meetings providing safeguarding and consistency. Only 18% of those work in teams of three or more and this was much more likely in AHSS than in STEM subjects. Discussions about role allocation and who does what in supervisory contexts are not routine (32% said it was on a case-by-case basis, 9% reported these decisions were made informally, and 8% stated they were either poorly defined or not defined at all). This is not per se, a problem; supervisors use their experience and professional judgement to ascertain what the candidate needs in the way of support. However, a significant **70% of respondents working in supervisory teams felt that the team model offered a better experience for doctoral candidates** (up from 65% in 2021) with those in teams of three or more likely to agree (78%). Calibrated with data from the Postgraduate Research Experience Survey (PRES) 2023 which revealed that only 57% of respondents believe they have “opportunities to become involved in the wider research community” it may be worth considering when putting a supervisory team together, the extent to which the collective experience of those involved can adequately support the individual researcher in becoming part of an active research culture and in developing a range of career-related skills and knowledge.

Examples of supervisory teams that include supervisors from outside HE are relatively low (19%) in the survey. The RSVP focus groups suggest that this cross-sector team is more common in professional-based (Management, Health Sciences) or performance-based (Theatre, Film, Music) programmes where cross fertilisation from industry and creative industry is an integral part of the doctorate. As the trend towards hybrid supervision continues and is enjoyed by candidates (PRES shows 83% satisfaction with hybrid learning) it is now easier to bring in supervisors from outside the institution and sector, or at least ‘advisers’ from outside the sector to provide intelligence, methodological and commercial expertise and international perspectives. There is also the potential to fill the gap in experience or confidence in areas such as providing advice on non-academic careers (see [Figure 32](#)).

Time and Workload Allocation

The data reconfirms the findings from 2021, that time allocation, where provided, does not match the time invested by supervisors. This is perhaps not surprising – many academics

invest discretionary time and effort making their actual workload far greater than the 100% allocated – yet what the data and the interactions with supervisors via the RSVP project indicate is that the nature of the supervisory relationship is a uniquely challenging and rewarding aspect of academic practice. The sense of duty and commitment to the individual over a three-to-seven-year period (depending on the mode of registration) impacts upon the kinds of support, guidance and expertise a doctoral candidate is likely to need. There is evidence in the qualitative feedback in the survey of benevolence and of ‘going the extra mile’ to help doctoral researchers conduct high quality, original, ethically responsible research and to support them through the personal and career challenges that naturally occur in an extended working relationship.

It is accepted practice within UK HEIs that individual institutions have autonomy over work-planning arrangements for their employees. Given the wide range of institution types, with concomitant balances between teaching, research and other activities (and incomes) it would not be a surprise to see variations in the ways that supervisory activity is work-planned. However, the data collated in Section 5 of this report does not simply show variation.

Rather it suggests a systemic mismatch between institutional and individual-academic understanding of the volume of activity associated with research degree supervision.

Both main and second supervisors are putting in additional hours, typically a third more than they are allocated. Further, there are those ‘hidden supervisors’ whose contributions to the doctoral endeavour go unrecorded by institutions – particularly postdocs, technicians and professional support staff.

This conclusion is further amplified by the suggestions set out in Section 10 for improving the supervisor experience – more time for supervisors to focus on their candidates and research being the most common request. Supervisors are supporting more students than they would ideally like and being allocated less time than they are contributing.

What Next?

We hope, in this report, to give a voice to the doctoral supervisors who invest time, effort and compassion to their researchers. They do this mainly out of love for research and a commitment to the next generation of researchers. As a sector, are we appropriately recognising, or capitalising on this investment?

Considerations for stakeholders

Below are a set of tentative suggestions based on the empirical data about how different stakeholders might wish to respond.

Funders	Maintain high expectations for engagement in CPD by supervisors of all doctoral researchers.
	Recognise the challenges associated with supporting a diversity of student identities (via, for example, a commitment to supervisor CPD) in indicators used when awarding or assessing doctoral provision.
	Develop an approach that sets research student stipends at a level that is attractive to high-performing individuals, and then maintains that level against nationally recognised comparators.
	Acknowledge the role that postdocs and Fellows play in supervision and make this part of grant and Fellowship applications. Also recognise in Focal and Landscape awards the need for CPD for supervision.
	Enhance supervisors' understanding of the different routes to doctoral funding. Consider developing guidelines for institutions to use as part of CPD.
Research Organisations	Review time-allocation practices for doctoral supervision and use this to interrogate mismatches with actual time spent on this activity. Include all those involved in supervision, including those who are often 'hidden' supervisors (typically early career researchers, technicians and professional service staff).
	Adopt mandatory training for new supervisors as part of probation and induction processes to inculcate good supervisory practice as well as awareness of institutional policies, principles, procedures.
	Maximise the use of team supervision (at least two people). This is recognised as beneficial for supervisors and candidates – provided that there is periodic discussion and agreement about roles and the expectations of all parties (supervisors and doctoral researchers).
	As part of discussions about research culture (and REF) consider how those involved in supervision can be recognised and valued.

11. Conclusions

Doctoral/Graduate Schools	<p>Consider the full spectrum of CPD and identify which elements are most suitable for different stages of supervisory experience. Those new to supervision may value mandatory induction training to help them understand the requirements (and those specific to the institution). More experienced supervisors are used to working collaboratively and prefer opportunities to learn from each other, share practice and reflect.</p>
	<p>Enable and enhance opportunities and structures to support supervisor confidence in talking about and signposting support for mental health and personal issues.</p>
	<p>Consider support and opportunities for supervisors to engage with the UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework and the UKCGE Research Supervision Recognition Programme.</p>
	<p>Consider the effective marketing and promotion of engagement in supervision as part of the core PGR offer. Prospective doctoral researchers and Funders may be attracted by an institutional commitment to excellence in supervisory practice.</p>
Supervisors	<p>Reflect on your supervisory practice – find appropriate ways to share positive or challenging experiences with colleagues or peers. Be a role model/mentor to a new supervisor.</p>
	<p>Seek out ways to develop your supervision and its contribution to your overall academic practice. Organisations such as the UKCGE regularly run in-person and online events covering a range of supervision-related topics (see references).</p>
	<p>Manage up – if you have ideas on how to improve supervision practice and culture or if something isn't working for you, raise it with someone who has the authority to change things ... particularly if it is something that resonates with the findings of this report.</p>
	<p>Engage with, invest in, and (ultimately) enjoy the process of developing your doctoral candidates into fully fledged researchers.</p>

Table 6. Considerations for stakeholders.

References:

Athena Swan Charter: <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/equality-charters/athena-swain-charter>

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Support for Postgraduate Research Students <https://www.officeforstudents.org.uk/for-providers/equality-of-opportunity/support-for-postgraduate-research-students/>

Postgraduate Research Experience Survey 2023: <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/reports-publications-and-resources/postgraduate-research-experience-survey-pres>

Research SuperVision Project (RSVP): <https://www.rsvp.ac.uk/>

UKCGE Events: <https://ukcge.ac.uk/events/forthcoming-events>

UKCGE Research Supervision Recognition Programme: <https://supervision.ukcge.ac.uk/>

UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework: <https://supervision.ukcge.ac.uk/good-supervisory-practice-framework>

UKRI New Deal for Postgraduate Research: <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/developing-people-and-skills/new-deal-for-postgraduate-research/>

Appendices

Role by career stage

Figure 40. "Which of the following best describe(s) your role?" And "How would you describe your current career stage?" 2024 = 5,174.

Number of candidates seen through to successful completion

Figure 41. Amended for 2024: "How many doctoral candidates have you seen through to successful completion in a formal role as supervisor?" Base n 2021 = 3,445; 2024 = 5,174.

Responses by subject

Subjects	%	n
Agriculture, Food and Veterinary Sciences	1%	69
Allied Health Professions, Dentistry, Nursing and Pharmacy	3%	180
Architecture, Built Environment and Planning	1%	70
Biological Sciences	12%	621
Chemistry	3%	154
Clinical Medicine	3%	139
Computer Science and Informatics	5%	259
Earth Systems and Environmental Sciences	2%	129
Engineering	8%	428
Mathematical Sciences	3%	175
Physics	4%	218
Psychology, Psychiatry and Neuroscience	6%	320
Public Health, Health Services and Primary Care	5%	267
Anthropology and Development Studies	<1%	25
Archaeology	1%	64
Area Studies	0%	11
Art and Design: History, Practice and Theory	3%	148
Business and Management Studies	6%	336
Classics	0%	14
Communication, Cultural and Media Studies, Library and Information Management	1%	71
Economics and Econometrics	1%	77
Education	6%	288
English Language and Literature	2%	117
Geography and Environmental Studies	2%	108
History	2%	123
Law	2%	97
Modern Languages and Linguistics	2%	90
Music, Drama, Dance, Performing Arts, Film and Screen Studies	2%	104
Philosophy	0%	23
Politics and International Studies	2%	91
Social Work and Social Policy	1%	74
Sociology	2%	128
Sport and Exercise Sciences, Leisure and Tourism	2%	103
Theology and Religious Studies	0%	23
Other	1%	30

Table 7. "What is your primary subject affiliation?" Base n = 5,174.

Disciplines included in overarching subject areas

STEM	AHSS
Agriculture, Food and Veterinary Sciences	Anthropology and Development Studies
Allied Health Professions, Dentistry, Nursing and Pharmacy	Archaeology
Architecture, Built Environment and Planning	Area Studies
Biological Sciences	Art and Design: History, Practice and Theory
Chemistry	Business and Management Studies
Clinical Medicine	Classics
Computer Science and Informatics	Communication, Cultural and Media Studies, Library and Information Management
Earth Systems and Environmental Sciences	Economics and Econometrics
Engineering	Education
Mathematical Sciences	English Language and Literature
Physics	Geography and Environmental Studies
Psychology, Psychiatry and Neuroscience	History
Public Health, Health Services and Primary Care	Law
	Modern Languages and Linguistics
	Music, Drama, Dance, Performing Arts, Film and Screen Studies
	Philosophy
	Politics and International Studies
	Social Work and Social Policy
	Sociology
	Sport and Exercise Sciences, Leisure and Tourism
	Theology and Religious Studies

Table 8. "What is your primary subject affiliation?" Base n = 5,174.

Full list of participating institutions

Institution	%	n	Institution	%	n
Abertay University	<1%	21	Leeds Beckett University	<1%	6
Aberystwyth University	1%	31	Leeds Trinity University	<1%	3
Anglia Ruskin University	1%	47	Liverpool Hope University	<1%	13
Aston University	<1%	15	Liverpool John Moores University	1%	56
Bangor University	<1%	6	Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine	<1%	19
Bath Spa University	<1%	12	London Business School	<1%	<3
Birkbeck, University of London	1%	30	London Metropolitan University	<1%	4
Birmingham City University	1%	36	London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, University of London	1%	52
Birmingham Newman University	<1%	<3	London South Bank University	<1%	10
Bishop Grosseteste University	<1%	6	Loughborough University	<1%	9
Bournemouth University	1%	42	Manchester Metropolitan University	2%	101
BPP University	<1%	<3	Middlesex University	<1%	23
Brunel University London	2%	111	Newcastle University	1%	70
Buckinghamshire New University	<1%	3	Northumbria University	1%	58
Canterbury Christ Church University	<1%	<3	Nottingham Trent University	1%	65
Cardiff Metropolitan University	1%	28	Oxford Brookes University	<1%	3
Cardiff University	1%	53	Plymouth Marjon University	<1%	8
City, University of London	1%	37	Queen Margaret University	<1%	21
Coventry University	1%	38	Queen Mary University of London	1%	41
Cranfield University	<1%	11	Queen's University Belfast	2%	78
De Montfort University	<1%	9	Regent's University London	<1%	<3
Durham University	3%	124	Robert Gordon University	<1%	<3
Edge Hill University	<1%	18	Royal College of Art	<1%	13
Edinburgh Napier University	<1%	16	Royal College of Music	<1%	<3
Falmouth University	<1%	<3	Royal Holloway, University of London	1%	46
Glasgow Caledonian University	<1%	6	Royal Northern College of Music	<1%	6
Goldsmiths, University of London	<1%	7	Sheffield Hallam University	1%	55
Guildhall School of Music and Drama	<1%	<3	Solent University	<1%	<3
Harper Adams University	<1%	10	St George's, University of London	<1%	16
Hartpury University and Hartpury College	<1%	5	St Mary's University, Twickenham	<1%	5
Heriot-Watt University	<1%	8	Staffordshire University	<1%	5
I'd prefer not to say	2%	105	Swansea University	1%	72
Imperial College London	2%	117	Teesside University	<1%	5
Keele University	1%	29	The Open University	1%	53
King's College London	4%	212	The Royal Veterinary College	<1%	20
Kingston University	1%	51	University of London	<1%	20
Lancaster University	<1%	8			

Institution	%	n	Institution	%	n
The University of Northampton	<1%	6	University of Liverpool	2%	75
Trinity Laban Conservatoire of Music and Dance	<1%	<3	University of London	<1%	7
Ulster University	2%	97	University of Manchester	4%	204
University College Birmingham	<1%	<3	University of Nottingham	3%	124
University College London	3%	143	University of Oxford	1%	34
University for the Creative Arts	<1%	10	University of Plymouth	1%	60
University of Aberdeen	<1%	8	University of Portsmouth	1%	59
University of Bath	1%	67	University of Reading	1%	45
University of Bedfordshire	<1%	5	University of Roehampton	<1%	<3
University of Birmingham	2%	85	University of Salford	<1%	6
University of Bradford	<1%	5	University of Sheffield	4%	174
University of Brighton	<1%	4	University of South Wales	<1%	23
University of Bristol	2%	119	University of Southampton	3%	161
University of Buckingham	<1%	<3	University of St Andrews	<1%	10
University of Cambridge	3%	161	University of Stirling	<1%	8
University of Central Lancashire	<1%	24	University of Strathclyde	1%	38
University of Chester	<1%	13	University of Suffolk	<1%	15
University of Chichester	<1%	<3	University of Sunderland	<1%	4
University of Cumbria	<1%	<3	University of Surrey	1%	50
University of Derby	1%	35	University of Sussex	1%	34
University of Dundee	1%	68	University of the Arts London	1%	52
University of East Anglia	1%	57	University of the Highlands and Islands	<1%	3
University of East London	<1%	<3	University of the West of England	1%	50
University of Edinburgh	3%	147	University of the West of Scotland	<1%	12
University of Essex	<1%	16	University of Wales Trinity Saint David	<1%	15
University of Exeter	2%	103	University of Warwick	1%	39
University of Glasgow	4%	184	University of West London	<1%	4
University of Gloucestershire	<1%	14	University of Westminster	<1%	18
University of Greenwich	<1%	8	University of Winchester	<1%	13
University of Hertfordshire	<1%	5	University of Wolverhampton	<1%	4
University of Huddersfield	1%	53	University of Worcester	<1%	15
University of Hull	1%	32	University of York	2%	99
University of Kent	<1%	<3	Wrexham University	<1%	<3
University of Leeds	3%	134	York St John University	<1%	9
University of Leicester	1%	38			
University of Lincoln	1%	29			

Table 9. List of participating institutions.

Respondents by region

Figure 42. "Which region of the UK do you live in?" Base n 2024 = 3,057.

Other respondent demographics

Figure 43. New Q 2024: “Are you a person living with a disability or long-term health condition?” Base 2024 = 4,830.

Figure 45. New Q 2024: “Which nation best represents your national identity?” Base n 2024 = 4,872.

Figure 44. New Q 2024: “Which of the following best describes your sexual orientation?” Base n 2024 = 4,831

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Figure 34.	71	Figure 41.	91
<p>“Which of the following do you do to enhance your supervisory practice?” Base n (2024) = 4,939. Base n (2021) = 3,435. Cross analysed with “Have you engaged with the UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework?” Derived variable created by merging ‘No, but I am aware of it’ with ‘No and I am not aware of it’. Base n = 4,939.</p>		<p>Amended for 2024: “How many doctoral candidates have you seen through to successful completion in a formal role as supervisor?” Base n 2021 = 3,445; 2024 = 5,174.</p>	
Figure 35.	72	Table 7.	92
<p>“Have you engaged with the UKCGE Good Supervisory Practice Framework?” Base n (2024) = 4,939. Base n (2021) = 3,435.</p>		<p>“What is your primary subject affiliation?” Base n = 5,174.</p>	
Figure 36.	74	Table 8.	93
<p>“How often does your workplace/ institution provide the following?” Base n = 4,923-4,927.</p>		<p>“What is your primary subject affiliation?” Base n = 5,174.</p>	
Figure 37.	75	Table 9.	95
<p>“To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the support available to you from your workplace/institution?” Only responses with notable differences between years shown. Base n (2021) = 3,435. Base n (2024) = 4,866-4,870.</p>		<p>List of participating institutions.</p>	
Figure 38.	77	Figure 42.	96
<p>“To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the support available to you from your workplace/institution?” Base n (2021) = 0-3,435. Base n (2024) = 4,866-4,875.</p>		<p>“Which region of the UK do you live in?” Base n 2024 = 3,057.</p>	
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<p>“Which of the following best describe(s) your role?” And “How would you describe your current career stage?” 2024 = 5,174.</p>			

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